

ICCM22 MELBOURNE AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

The deformation and failure response of UHMW-PE composite to localised blast loading

Long H. Nguyen¹, Ali Daliri^{1,2}, Richard Curry³, Genevieve S. Langdon³, Huon Bornstein¹

¹ Defence Science and Technology Group, Australia

² School of Engineering, RMIT University, Australia

³ Blast and Impact Survivability Research Unit, University of Cape Town, South Africa

Introduction

Composites reinforced with ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMW-PE) fibres have been extensively studied and used in ballistic protection application as it provides high protection at relatively low weight. There are very few studies on its blast performance and application within this area remains limited. In this work, experiments were conducted to subject UHMW-PE composite to localised blast loading. The rupture threshold and dynamic deformation were measured and the damage and failure mechanisms of the material were investigated.

Experiment

Target material

Dyneema® HB26 was used, which consisted of a polyurethane matrix reinforced with ~17 µm diameter UHMW-PE fibres with a fibre volume fraction of approximately 83%. The uni-directional prepreg was laid up in a cross ply layup $[0/90]_{80}$ and hot pressed at 128°C and 20 MPa to form a laminate. The laminate is approximately 10 mm thick, with the following lateral dimension 400x400mm.

Experimental setup

Blast tests were performed at BISRU UCT with the target bolted to a target frame mounted to a pendulum, allowing the impulse from the blast to be measured. A 50 mm diameter cylindrical PE4 explosive charge at a fixed stand off distance (SOD) of 50 mm from the target was used to provide the blast load.

Blast pendulum at BISRU UCT (courtesy of McDonald et al. 2018)

High speed camera setup within blast pendulum (courtesy of Curry & Langdon 2017)

Performance Metrics

Rupture threshold: To determine the threshold at which the target is at the limit of rupture, the charge mass was varied until the difference between the lowest charge causing rupture (perforated) and the highest charge without rupture was within 5 g of explosive.

Dynamic deformation: The transient deformation of the target under blast loading was measured using two high speed cameras housed within the pendulum. The images were analysed using digital image correlation.

Results

Rupture threshold

The rupture threshold of a 10 mm thick Dyneema® HB26 target is between 25-30 g of PE4 at 50 mm SOD. At close to the rupture threshold, melting occurred on the front face and significant permanent bulge deformation occurred with reverse snap buckling of the central region.

Target from 25 g PE4 charge (top) and 30 g charge resulting in perforation (bottom). From left to right: strike face, rear face and perspective view of the target

Dynamic deformation

DIC was performed with charges below the rupture threshold. At 10 g, the centre point deformation rises rapidly and then stays constant. For 15 and 20 g charge, the centre point increases rapidly and then inverts due to elastic recovery, leading to reversed snap buckling (RSB).

Failure mode

Scanning electron micrographs of the failed fibres show failure by tensile stretching, necking and fibrillation.

Fibre on the strike face

Fibre on the mid-plane

Fibre on the back face

Conclusion

Localised blast tests were performed on UHMW-PE composite to investigate the response of the material to blast loading. The rupture threshold was determined for a 10 mm thick target and the failed fibres showed failure in tension via straining, necking and fibrillation. The deformation response was measured and showed that close to the rupture threshold, the panel would load then elastically recover, leading to reversed snap buckling of the panel and a central depression was formed. The results provided initial insight into the response of this material to localised blast loading and will form the basis for future numerical model development and validation.